

CADRE: Coordinated Access for Data and Research Environments

Governance of Sensitive Qualitative Data Across Sectors: Interim Report

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GOVERNANCE OF SENSITIVE QUALITATIVE DATA ACROSS SECTORS

INTERIM REPORT¹

1 Introduction

The governance of sensitive data is a significant concern for governments, evident in debates surrounding legislation and policy frameworks. Funding bodies, governments, and researchers worldwide have increasingly called for greater adoption of open access data principles, the benefits and risks of which have been brought into sharp relief by the COVID-19 pandemic. Open access data encompasses a range of data types, some of which contain more sensitive content than others and, hence, governance implications and ethical protocols can vary.

In Australia, the governance of sensitive data has recently focused on the *Data Availability and Transparency Bill 2020* (DAT Bill 2020), with protocols for the sharing of data based on the Five Safes Framework (Desai, Ritchie & Welpton 2016). In legislation and associated discussions regarding data use and reuse, ‘data’ is commonly presumed to be either quantitative data or large-scale datasets, with limited consideration of how differences between quantitative and qualitative (or between structured and unstructured) or the size of the datasets might affect how they are handled, managed, and access risks understood.

Universities and the GLAMR (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums & Records) sectors, as with all entities and individuals in Australia, are beholden to Federal legislation when handling data. These two sectors, however, regularly collect, store, share, and reuse *qualitative* (or unstructured) data (particularly but not only in the humanities, arts, social sciences [HASS] disciplines) in addition to *quantitative* (or structured) data. Qualitative or unstructured data has its own unique qualities, which bring specific challenges for governance of sensitive data and attendant potential risks for participants.

This interim report examines governance of sensitive qualitative data in the university and GLAMR sectors and considers how this data is handled in terms of security and privacy. This includes risks associated with anonymisation or lack thereof, as well as changing contexts of data and implications for ongoing consent. It asks whether provisions are made for qualitative data that properly take account of their unique qualities and high potential for privacy risks in comparison to the risks usually associated with quantitative and de-identified data. It also briefly comments on the Five Safes framework as it relates to qualitative data, in anticipation of a longer analysis of this framework and qualitative data.

¹ Version 1.0 of this report was submitted on 28 April 2022. Thanks to those that provided feedback for this published version: the CADRE Content working group, including Steven McEachern, Ingrid Mason, Jatender Mohal, Yolante Jones, Heather Leasor, and Phi Bang Nguyen; as well as Robin Burgess, Roxanne Missingham. The report, with feedback taken under consideration was published online in January 2023. All information is accurate as of 28 April 2022. As noted, some information, codes, and legislation were under review at the time of that original submission. The versions utilised here date from that first submission date.

It should be noted that this interim report is an initial scoping document that focuses on governance of qualitative or unstructured data rather than sensitive data in general. This is in order to canvass any potential considerations required for this particular type of data on the CADRE platform project. As an interim report, it is not intended to be comprehensive in scope but draws on several case studies, including operationalisation of legislation and policy at the University of Melbourne. The final report, due in 2023, will provide a broader investigation/review of case studies drawn from Australian and international higher education institutions. This report is a companion to other CADRE reports, including the *CADRE Five Safes Framework*, a document currently being drafted by the CADRE Content Working Group.²

The report is divided into five sections, including the Introduction. The second section gives a summary of relevant government legislation. The next two provide an overview of the governance of qualitative data in academic research overall and in tertiary institutions, using the University of Melbourne as a case study. Section Five looks at the practice of data sharing in the GLAMR (galleries, libraries, archives, museums, and records) sector, including digitisation and open access to collections.

1.1 Qualitative data: definitions and descriptions

The *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research* defines qualitative research as that “involving the ... use of empirical materials such as case studies, personal experience, life stories, interviews, observations, and cultural texts” (NHMRC 2007/2018). Qualitative research data seeks to capture the quality and texture of phenomena, social interactions, and experiences through a range of research methods. The aim of these methods is not to produce numerical data but convey the character and context of subjective experience. Some protocols for sharing quantitative data through archiving and secondary analysis can be applied to qualitative research ‘but there are obvious and well-documented differences in the type of data and process[es] for eliciting or collecting data, in negotiating the context of the original study and in how data are recontextualised in any subsequent interpretation’ (McLeod, O’Connor & Davis 2020).

In the university sector, particularly across the HASS disciplines, a wide range of qualitative data is collected and retained during research projects.³ The GLAMR sector too collects such data and holds a significant amount within their formal collections. The type of data that these sectors hold, and potentially share and use/re-use is wide ranging. It includes audio and video interviews, transcripts of interviews, visual culture artefacts, manuscripts, research notes, personal biographical data, material culture (e.g., photographs, ephemera), maps, stories and more. The Qualitative Data Repository (QDR) gives a detailed, although not exhaustive, list [on their website of types of qualitative data](#) (QDR n.d.b). The data generated through qualitative methods, such as interviews, focus groups, fieldwork observations, photographs, is typically information rich, containing, for example, social insights, direct

² Some of the observations in this report have also been utilised in the *Five Safes Framework* currently being drafted by the CADRE Content Working Group (CADRE 2022). Version 1.0 is available on [Zenodo](#).

³ Although often associated primarily with HASS, it is not limited to this field. Qualitative research has been used in other fields such as Physiotherapy (e.g., see the work of Suzanne Gough, Bond University; [Shane Pritchard](#), Monash University), Medicine ([VanDeVusse and Mueller 2021](#); [Jennerich 2021](#)). As of 28 February 2022, QDR had 96 projects from Social Sciences, 30 from Medicine, Health & Life Sciences, and Other (18), which make up the bulk of the projects. Smaller numbers from Earth & Environmental Sciences, Agricultural Sciences, Law, Business and Management, and Computer and Information Science are also present (QDR n.d.a).

observations of or reflections upon personal experiences, details of historical events, data on individuals and groups, and descriptive detail of local contexts and settings more.

Due to the richness of this data, the risks associated with it are correspondingly high. But this richness is also why it has great potential for sharing and re-use by others, either in the current moment to understand the present or in the future for the purposes of what would be more historically focused research. Even when anonymised, this data contains significant Personally Identifiable Information (PII) that might render a participant, third party or group as identifiable, making it very high-risk data.⁴ For example, in interviews about an education or social policy development, a prominent figure in political or education administration circles might be easily identified through background or contextual details revealed during the interview due to, for example, the position they hold, despite anonymisation. They might also inadvertently provide sufficient information about the lives and experiences of others to also identify these third parties. Applications of machine learning to such data, rich in contextual detail, might also increase chances of reidentification (Weitzenboeck et al., 2022).⁵

2 Summary of relevant government legislation

2.1 Productivity Commissioner and Report

Data governance (including access, use and reuse) has over the last few years been the subject in Australia of new government assessments and legislation. From 2016 to 2017, the federal Productivity Commission conducted and published the results of an enquiry “into ways to improve the availability and use of public and private sector data” ([Productivity Commission n.d.](#)). The Commission’s brief was to:

- look at the benefits and costs of making public and private datasets more available
- examine options for collection, sharing and release of data
- identify ways consumers can use and benefit from access to data, particularly data about themselves
- consider how to preserve individual privacy and control over data use ([Productivity Commission n.d.](#))

One of the results of the enquiry and report ([Productivity Commission 2017](#)) was the identification of

a number of barriers inhibiting the better use of data ... [and the recommendation of] a legislative pathway to modernise Australia’s regulatory framework governing data availability and use ([Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet n.d.](#)),

This legislative pathway would also interact with current privacy laws and secrecy provisions to allow improved access to government data. This included the establishment of “institutional and governance arrangements including Accredited Data Authorities and a

⁴ “Information that can be used on its own or with other information to identify, contact or locate a single person, or to identify an individual in context.” Australian Signals Directorate, ‘[Personally identifiable information \(PII\)](#)’, *Australian Cybersecurity Centre*.

⁵ Weitzenboeck et al., 2022, also give the example of court cases where enough information is given about individuals to reidentify, especially if then linked to other datasets.

trusted user framework to facilitate better sharing of data”. ([Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet n.d.](#))

This led to the drafting of the DAT Bill 2020, which was in its first reading at time of writing,⁶ which will

authorise *public sector data*⁷ *custodians* to share data with accredited users in accordance with specific authorisations, purposes, principles and agreements; specifies the specific responsibilities imposed on data scheme entities; establishes and specifies the functions and powers of the National Data Commissioner as the regulator of the scheme; establishes and specifies the functions and membership of the National Data Advisory Council as an advisory body to the commissioner in relation to sharing and use of public sector data; and establishes the regulation and enforcement framework for the scheme [italics added]. ([Parliament of Australia, n.d.](#))

The *DAT Bill*, together with the *Privacy Act 1988*, is intended as part of a suite of legislation that directs the use of Commonwealth public sector data and informs the framework of data governance for Commonwealth organisations (see e.g., [AIHW 2021a, Data Governance Framework](#)). The Intergovernmental Agreement on Data Sharing (2021), signed between the Commonwealth and the states and territories, also allows for sharing between agencies in these jurisdictions. Commonwealth government entities also follow the Protective Security Policy Framework, which includes policies on Personnel and Information Security ([Attorney General’s Department n.d.](#))

The DAT Bill will provide the legislative basis for the (already-established) Office of the National Data Commissioner (ONDC) which “is responsible for streamlining how public sector data is used and shared” ([ONDC n.d.](#)).

The data sharing principles informing the bill are based on the Five Safes framework. In the interim period before the bill is passed, the ONDC established five data sharing principles based on the Five Safes to “to assist agencies [such as the Australian Institute of Health and Welfare (AIHW) as part of their data governance (AIHW 2021, 7, 52–53)] holding Australian Government data (data custodians) to safely and effectively share ... data”:

1. Projects: Data is shared for an appropriate purpose that delivers a public benefit.
2. People: The user has the appropriate authority to access the data.
3. Settings: The environment in which the data is shared minimises the risk of unauthorised use or disclosure.
4. Data: Appropriate and proportionate protections are applied to the data.
5. Output: The output from the data sharing arrangement is appropriately safeguarded before any further sharing or release. ([Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet 2019, 6](#))

⁶ The resulting *Data Availability and Transparency Act 2022* was registered on 4 April 2022 after this draft was submitted. The implications of this Act will be fully discussed in the final version of this report, released in 2023.

⁷ “Public sector data is defined as data lawfully created, collected or held by or on behalf of Commonwealth bodies” ([Parliament of the Commonwealth of Australia 2020, 3](#)).

The Five Safes framework has also been adopted by some state governments for data governance, including South Australia’s ‘Trusted Access Principles’ in the *Public Sector (Data Sharing) Act 2016* (Government of South Australia, n.d.); New South Wales (Data.NSW 2020); and Victoria (Victorian Government, n.d.).

The [Privacy Act 1988](#), as well as state and territory privacy legislation (e.g., *Privacy and Data Protection Act 2014* [Vic]), are also relevant to the use of qualitative and unstructured data. The *Privacy Act*

was introduced to promote and protect the privacy of individuals and to regulate how Australian Government agencies and organisations with an annual turnover of more than \$3 million, and [some other organisations](#), handle [personal information](#). (OAIC n.d.)

The *Australian Privacy Principles* (APP) assist application of the *Privacy Act 1988*. APP 2 ‘Anonymity and Pseudonymity’ provides “that individuals must have the option of dealing anonymously or by pseudonym with an APP entity” (OAIC 2019, Chapter 2, 3), which “enable[s them] [in order]... to exercise greater control over their personal information and decide how much personal information will be shared or revealed to others” (OAIC 2019, Chapter 2, 4). This would allow for personal information to be revealed in qualitative/unstructured research, subject to the informed consent of the participants and any requests for anonymisation made by them.

An examination of the Productivity Commissioner’s Report and the current proposed DAT does not specifically make mention of qualitative data. The latter simply defines ‘Data’ as “any information in a form capable of being communicated, analysed or processed (whether by an individual or by computer or other automated means)” ([DAT Bill, 5](#)). While this definition does not specifically exclude qualitative data, it defines data in a way that is arguably more amenable to the communication and processing of numerical or quantitative datasets.

2.2 Qualitative data in the government realm

While the above legislation and reporting does not specifically differentiate between qualitative and quantitative data, the former represents a substantial body of potentially shareable government data. Commonwealth departments such as AIHW and AIFS hold significant collections of qualitative data relating to their research (including that collected by consultants and in conjunction with university researchers).⁸ The AIHW data governance framework does not specifically differentiate between qualitative and quantitative data in its handling of data, but its definition of data does suggest that qualitative data is in its purview:

⁸ This includes projects such as the mixed-methods *Ten to Men: The Australian Longitudinal Study on Male Health*, commissioned by Department of Health, initially conducted by University of Melbourne ([Ten to Men 2022](#)) and managed by the AIFS, with data held on the ADA Dataverse ([ADA Dataverse n.d.](#)). AIFS holds a large number of qualitative and mixed-mode studies: 22% of assets are qualitative, with another 25% mixed-mode studies. Some notable research funded by Attorney General’s Department, including Independent Children’s Lawyer (ICL) Study; The Children and Young People in Separated Families project; Elder Abuse Prevalence Study; Legal Partnerships Evaluation (Pilot A): Qualitative studies of staff from FRCs and Legal Services and clients participating in the Legal Partnerships Program (email with Jatender Mohal, 16 November 2021).

measurements and observations, including facts, figures, records, statistics or opinions, whether true or not, that have been collected directly or obtained as a by-product of a compliance, regulatory or service-delivery process. Data includes information about persons, businesses and other organisations and their characteristics, practices and activities. (AIHW 2021, 63)

The AIHW framework specifies the de-identification of data as complying with the relevant legislation and their confidentiality obligations but importantly states:

From the perspectives of the Privacy Act and the AIHW Act, it is neither realistic nor expected that AIHW remove the risk of re-identification entirely. Rather, we must mitigate the risk until it is very low: until there is no reasonable risk of re-identification occurring (AIHW 2021, 13)

Most federal, state, and municipal governments have GLAMR institutions which hold large amounts of qualitative data and usually have their own data governance frameworks. These adhere to applicable state and federal legislation and might be included in or in addition to collections management plans and other policies. They are also guided by data management processes for their individual section of government or by legislation at various levels of government. For example, the National Archives of Australia ([NAA 2021](#)) has obligations with regard to long-term preservation and sharing of data under the *Archives Act 1983*, and follows the Information Management Standard for Australian Government as part of their data governance ([NAA n.d.](#)). GLAMR organisations will be discussed in detail in Section 5 below.

3 Governance of Qualitative Data in Academic Research

3.1 Research funding, codes of conduct and ethical frameworks

Australian universities are subject to a range of legislation, codes and frameworks that govern their research activities. While much of the legislation is binding, some codes operate more as guidelines for best practice.

The Federal Productivity Commission's report into data availability and use, for example, saw

a possible application of the [Five Safes] frameworks ... to publicly funded data – explicitly referencing data generated by academic research that is funded through public grants (such as the Australian Research Council). While this proposal was not taken up by the Commonwealth in their implementation of data sharing policy, it has impacted on the policy development of particular research institutions. (Five Safes Framework v.1.0.1, 14)

The [National Health and Medical Research Council Act 1992](#) is relevant to research governance in Australia. The Act established and governs the NHMRC, the focus of which is funding for medical research, and it also sets ethical codes for research in this arena and more widely. The NHMRC has statutory obligations arising from the [NHMRC Act](#) “for supporting health and medical research; for developing health advice for the Australian community, health professionals and governments; and for providing advice on ethical behaviour in health care and in the conduct of health and medical research” ([Health Direct, n.d.](#); [NHMRC, n.d.](#)).

There are a number of other codes that have bearing on government research data or on the bodies that govern and collect them, such as the “Public Governance, Performance and Accountability Act 2013 (PGPA Act), the Public Service Act 1999, and other legislation and regulations as determined by the Public Service Commission” (NHMRC, n.d.)

3.1.1 Codes of conduct

The [*Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research*](#) (NHMRC 2018) (henceforth *Australian Code*) and the [*National Statement on the Ethical Conduct of Human Research*](#) (NHMRC 2007/2018) (henceforth, *National Statement*) are two key regulatory frameworks for academic research. These statements were developed by the two principal national research funding councils – the NHMRC, the ARC – and the peak organisation representing all Australian universities, Universities Australia. These must be adhered to in order to be eligible for ARC or NHMRC research funding. In addition, there are ethical codes related to with First Nations (Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander) peoples: the AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research, governed by the Australian Institute for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (AIATSIS, 2020)

The *Australian Code* is accompanied by a series of guides on implementing the code and determining breaches such as authorship concerns or data misuse. In addition, the *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Research* provides detailed guidance on how to adhere to the code. The statement includes details on the sharing and reuse of data and recommends a Data Management Plan, listing key considerations for the handling of data that should be considered in the plan:

- a) physical, network, system security and any other technological security measures;
- b) policies and procedures;
- c) contractual and licensing arrangements and confidentiality agreements;
- d) training for members of the project team and others, as appropriate;
- e) the form in which the data or information will be stored;
- f) the purposes for which the data or information will be used and/or disclosed;
- g) the conditions under which access to the data or information may be granted to others; and
- h) what information from the data management plan, if any, needs to be communicated to potential participants.” (NHMRC 2018, s.3.1.46)

These codes are compulsory for any research undertaken that is funded by the NHMRC or the ARC and highly recommended for other research (NHMRC 2018, 1) and many universities have incorporated adherence to them into their research policies.

The *AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research* is also a key framework for any research involving First Nations people in Australia. This code will be analysed in further detail in the final version of this report, to be submitted mid-2023.

3.1.2 Research funding bodies and data governance

Research funding bodies often require such codes and frameworks to be followed by those provided with funding through various schemes – most often, university academics or joint research projects with external parties.

For the Humanities, Arts and Social Sciences, disciplines which generate a significant volume and range of qualitative data, the chief funding body is the ARC. Some strands of health and medical research also incorporate qualitative data and are governed by the NHMRC.

The ARC ([n.d.a](#)) [lists the range of codes and guidelines](#), including those above, designed to “encourage responsible research practices”; and “all Proposals and ARC-funded research Projects are either recommended or required to conform to the principles outlined in the following and their successor documents, as stipulated within the scheme-specific funding rules”. The ARC also has its ARC Open Access Policy (2017), which stipulates that “Any Research Outputs arising from an ARC supported research Project must be made openly accessible within a twelve (12) month period from the date of publication.”

The ARC requires researchers to create a data management plan from the beginning of the research project, outlining “how data will be collected, formatted, described, stored and shared throughout, and beyond, the project lifecycle.” This requirement is consistent with the *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research* and guided by the [OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding \(2007\)](#).

The ARC’s requirement is designed to encourage researchers to consider the ways in which they can best manage, store, disseminate and reuse data. Researchers, in consultation with institutions, have a responsibility to consider the management and future potential of their research data, taking into account the particular approaches, standards and uses for data that may exist in different institutions, disciplines and research projects. ([ARC n.d.b](#))

It should be noted, though, that while there is a requirement to create the plan, there are few mechanisms to monitor implementation of the plan, rendering a potential disconnect between, planning, intentions and actual practices.

While the ARC does not currently mandate open data for researchers, considering the possibilities of sharing and re-use of data is encouraged in order to maximise “the benefits from ARC-funded research, including by ensuring greater access to research data” ([ARC 2019](#)). Funding bodies mandating or encouraging sharing and re-use of data or even open data⁹ has a number of motivations, including desire to:

derive *maximum benefit* from [their] investment in research, ... calls for greater *public accountability*, corresponding *institutional protocols* for managing these requirements, ... the greater *regulation and monetization* of data more generally ... [and] the growing reach of open research agendas that invoke *egalitarian and democratic possibilities* in making research more widely and freely available [Emphases added]. ([McLeod & O’Connor 2021](#), 524)

3.1.3 Requirements of peak bodies and organisations

As the ARC notes above, specific approaches to the management of data may exist in different disciplines and, by extension, peak bodies and organisations that have ethical

⁹ Lists of institutions, funding bodies and other organisations that mandate open access can be found on the ROARMAP (Registry of Open Access Repository Mandates and Policies) website ([University of Southampton n.d.](#)).

guidelines regarding sensitive qualitative data to which members are expected to conform (and which guide those in the field that are not members).

In the HASS field in Australia, there are numerous individual peak bodies and organisations, including the Australian Historical Association (AHA), The Australian Sociological Association (TASA), Oral History Australia (OHA) and Australian Association for Research in Education (AARE).¹⁰ The ethical codes or guidelines for these four are summarised below.

Of the four, the OHA and AARE have the most detailed guidance for the governance of data in the field. This is considered this at the heart of best practice for oral historians and as consistent with an ethos of listening to and documenting the voices of those whose experiences have not usually been captured in written records. In the case of the AHA and TASA, the word ‘data’ is referred to rarely, although it should be understood in terms of the more generic descriptor of ‘research’ and, in the case of the AHA might be considered as part of the more generic and overarching terms of ‘sources’, ‘archival materials’ and ‘information’.

None of these guidelines make specific reference to privacy or future data management legislation, although the AHA does require members to be aware of all relevant legislation.

In these cases, there is no specific differentiation between qualitative and quantitative data. Those researching in these fields often use a variety of data types and there is range of research materials that might reveal information with sensitive components. This is also reflected in the concern in these ethical guidelines for the privacy and confidentiality of the data, including that of research participants, which acknowledges the potential sensitivity of such data.

3.1.3.1 AHA Code of Ethics

The AHA’s ethical code (n.d.) is surprisingly brief and incorporates a code of conduct, which is a separate code in the case of TASA. As with the latter, the specific pieces of legislation to which it refers are anti-discrimination and human rights related legislation and not any privacy or data legislation, although the latter is suggested in section 13.

The topic of privacy and governance or management of research data is not specifically referred to in the AHA code, but it might be considered inherent in some of the provisions that mention research and outputs, including those that mention the broader term ‘sources’. These include:

3. Members shall not refuse any reasonable request to share their knowledge or expertise and shall as far as possible make available the sources to which they have had access.
5. Members should respect the rights of oral history participants by acknowledging their contributions, or not, according to their informants’ wishes.
7. Members shall make reasonable efforts to ensure the preservation of archival materials that appear to be at risk through neglect, threat of destruction, or any other cause.

¹⁰ There are numerous other professional organisations and bodies with ethical guidelines that might be informative and could be considered in the final version of this report. These include: [Australian Political Studies Association](#) and [Australian Population Association](#).

10. Members shall not, without due permission, use any confidential information acquired during the course of their work for personal advantage or for the advantage of a co-worker or third person. Nor shall members use such information to the disadvantage of an employer/client nor disclose such information, except where such disclosure may be required by law.

13. Members shall take care to inform themselves of and to comply with all legal requirements relating to their work.

3.1.3.2 TASA Code of Ethics

TASA Members follow a [Code of Ethics \(n.d.\)](#), which draws “on internationally accepted principles” and is influenced by the codes of ethics and practices adopted by a number of international sociological organisations, university Human Ethics guidelines, the NHMRC and the AIHW.

Some specific aspects of this code relate or refer to data governance, particularly regarding the ethical treatment of research participants, chiefly the maintenance of their confidentiality/anonymity. These include: gaining informed consent from participants; de-identification of data where appropriate; “careful and secure storage of research data”, maintenance of confidentiality; critical examination of research practices that might cause harm. The code does not make reference to privacy legislation and does not directly mention the future re-use of data.

Data Governance is also hinted at in a section on ‘Contractual Research, Clients and Sponsors’ in which it states that “the privacy of research information is a matter for negotiation and agreement between the parties to the research” and that TASA members should clarify, prior to research commencement,

1. the right of the researcher to publish research and information independently from the client, or to use the research results commercially or otherwise; and
2. the nature of the responsibility and liability of the researcher regarding any use made of the research results by the client once the research is complete.

Other items that point to issues of data governance include:

- the “responsibility to maintain high standards of competence and to maintain knowledge of current information and methods in the areas they are researching”;
- awareness of “statutory obligations to reveal information against the misuse of these results and where possible, take reasonable steps to correct any misuse or misrepresentation received in the course of research”;
- “Unless there are compelling reasons, research findings should be publicly accessible, especially to the participants”;
- “members should guard against the misuse of these results and where possible, take reasonable steps to correct any misuse or misrepresentation.”

Some of these guidelines specifically refer to the management of data, while others suggest it in vaguer terms of research and research results or understanding the application of research

methodologies. The idea of re-use of data is not specifically referred to but could be encompassed in the generic descriptor of ‘research results’.

3.1.3.3 OHA guidance for ethical practice

The OHA has a number of [detailed guidelines for the ethical practice of oral history \(OHA n.d.a\)](#), available on its website. These include: [Guidelines of Ethical Practice](#) (OHA 2007); [Ethics and University Research](#) (OHA n.d.c); [Practising Oral History](#) (OHA n.d.b); and [Training](#), all of which detail best-practice for oral historians.

The section on *Practising Oral History* (OHA n.d.b) itemises four key considerations for best practice, all of which relate to data management (including collection, storage, and suggestions for re-use in the future):

- ethical conduct and informed consent in interviews and post-production
- high quality recording
- well planned and executed oral history projects
- archiving oral history interviews for longevity and accessibility.

The *Guidelines for Ethical Practice in Oral History* (OHA 2007) provides further information on best practice in oral history, including data governance. They state:

Oral history involves recording, preserving and making available candid information that may be sensitive or confidential. All interviewers are asked to act to preserve the rights and responsibilities of the different parties involved and to refuse to work in any other way.

The OHA details other aspects of data management, including within the *University Ethical Approval of a Project involving Humans* document (OHA n.d.c), also refers to the ethics of oral history and its methodologies, including the management of data (where the data is largely related to oral history interviews).¹¹

There are five sections: Archival Aims, Anonymity, Copyright, Sensitive Topics, and Home Settings. The first four specifically centre around the collection, storage, sharing and re-use of data. OHA considers the preservation of the data as key to the practice of oral history:

A primary aim of oral history is to add previously unrecorded voices to the historical record, and oral history ethical guidelines stress the researcher’s responsibility to ensure the secure and permanent preservation of the interview, subject to the interviewee’s wishes. Oral history interviews are therefore usually recorded with a permanent archive status in mind.

It should be noted that for the OHA ‘data’ is usually the interviews conducted rather than other data associated with the interview, such as photographs or other artefacts and ephemera – although this would likely be considered implicit in these guidelines.

¹¹ This document was updated (in November 2022) after the writing of this report and the new version will be considered in the final version of the report.

3.1.3.4 AARE Code of Ethics

The Australian Association for Research in Education (AARE) Code of Ethics ([n.d.](#)) primarily focuses on data in terms of protecting privacy of and preventing harm to those involved in the research, including participants. There is no overt discussion of data management, governance, preservation, access, or future use but it does state that researchers:

should keep themselves informed on the methodology of research, including disputes about appropriate methodology. They should regularly reform their own methodology in the light of that discussion, and be rigorous in its application to their work. (AARE n.d., 9)

This would thus apply to current debates in the archiving, management, sharing and re-use of research data by education researchers. Likewise, the code specifies that those in the field should have appropriate training in research ethics, which also might apply to research data management methods and ethics.

Sharing of research with colleagues or in publications is mentioned in general terms but does not specifically discuss sharing of original datasets:

Researchers should make themselves aware of the impact of other research, including research in other sub-disciplines, upon their work. *They should offer their work for discussion from time to time by researchers in other subdisciplines* [italics added] (AARE n.d., 9)

They should report their findings fully without omission of significant data, disclosing details of their theories, methods and research designs which might bear upon interpretations of their findings. (AARE n.d., 10)

Researchers have a duty to disseminate research results to stakeholders, to other researchers, to their students and to the general public. The first duty of a researcher is to reach the widest possible audience, not to maximise personal benefit. (AARE n.d., 11)

Overall, these four bodies either encourage or mandate the sharing of research outputs while utilising methodologies appropriate to their fields, particularly regarding the preservation of participant privacy. Of the four bodies discussed, the OHA has the most detailed guidance for their members on the collection, storage, sharing and re-use of data in the future, where it mandates its members to always be cognisant of preservation and future use of the data collected.

The rapidly changing environment for data sharing is perhaps not so well reflected in these documents – other than in the example of OHA. Furthermore, the affordances and risks of digital data are not very explicit in these. Likewise, the distinction between sensitive and non-sensitive data is not so salient. Research drawn in studies governed by these codes is likely to be a mixture of structured and unstructured sources (or mixed methods) employed and this is not well reflected. The OHA guidelines, for instance, are more oriented to interpretive material and analysis of interview narratives.

3.2 Governance in tertiary institutions

Individual universities also have a range of policies and codes relevant to data management, which are informed by these overarching national research codes, policies, and frameworks, as well as relevant federal and state or territory legislation.

For this initial report, we take the University of Melbourne as our chief example, and an illustration of current practices at a large and research-intensive Australian university ([Group of Eight, n.d.](#)). A number of key policies regarding data governance are discussed below.

It should be noted that a number of these policies are under revision or development and, at the time of the final version of this report at the end of the CADRE project, the new policies and frameworks will be analysed.

In the final report, we will also consider other Australian tertiary institutions and their policies and compare these to those adopted at the University of Melbourne.

3.2.1 Management of Research Data & Records Policy ([MPF1242](#)) (University of Melbourne 2013)¹²

At the University of Melbourne, the chief data governance policy is the *Management of Research Data and Records Policy* ([MPF1242](#)) (University of Melbourne 2013). The policy (under revision at the time of writing) gives an overview of relevant commonwealth and state legislation, as well as national research codes and university regulations, under which it has been written and that researchers (including students, staff and honoraries) must follow.

These include, but are not limited to the [Privacy Act 1988 \(Cwlth\)](#), *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research 2007*, *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research*, [Public Records Act 1973 \(Vic\)](#), [Information Privacy Act 2000 \(Vic\)](#), Regulation 17.1.R8 - University Code of Conduct for Research.

As part of this policy, researchers are required to create Data Management Plans for their research projects and, in doing so, “develop appropriate processes for the collection, storage, use, re-use, access and retention of research data and records associated with their research program, including confidential research data and records” (MPF1242, 2.1). They must also “ensure that the integrity and security of their research data and records is maintained, and that this material is stored in a retrievable way” and

plan for the ongoing custodial responsibilities for the research data and records at the conclusion of the research project or on departure from the University, including information about access and potential re-use of the data and future deposit into open access research databases where such action complies with all legal, ethical and confidentiality agreements on the data, including copyright, privacy and intellectual property. (MPF1242, 2.2)

¹² This policy analysis was current at time of writing. The policy was under review at the time and updated 9 June 2022.

Much of this incorporates concerns for privacy and confidentiality of data, compliance with legal and ethical legislation, codes and frameworks, as well as the desire for data to be retrievable with the suggestion of future open access, sharing and re-use.

This policy is currently being revised by the university and part of it will include the University Research Data Classification Framework currently in draft form. This will establish a scaffold for sensitive data management and assist researchers in how to manage their data and their obligations in managing that data, including aiding with understanding of relevant legislation and policies, as well as a classification system for sensitive data.

The policy is linked to the university's participation in the "ARDC Institutional Underpinnings program [which] is uniting 25 Australian universities to develop a framework for managing research data." ([ARDC n.d.](#)). Part of the University of Melbourne program of work includes investigating management and storage of sensitive data, as well as its correlation with current University data, research management and ethics policies and training.

Other Australian universities, including the University of New South Wales ([2019](#)) and University of Newcastle ([2017](#)) have already developed such policies, frameworks and tools for their researchers. A comparison of frameworks between universities will be developed for the final report due in 2023.

3.2.2. Research Integrity and Misconduct Policy ([MPF1318](#)) (University of Melbourne 2020b)¹³

This policy (under revision at the time of writing) includes, but is not limited to, the management of research data, for which it sets out specific guidelines. In Section 5.1, researchers' responsibilities regarding their data. This includes requirements for:

- accuracy and detail of data to enable verification (and replicability) of results;
- durable and retrievable storage of data;
- retention for five years, or longer if the data meets specific criteria, including "if the data has historical or archival value";
- procedures in the research unit or department for retention of data, "normally kept in the department or unit"¹⁴; and
- availability of data to other researchers without breaching confidentiality.

3.2.3 Research Ethics and Biorisk Management Policy ([MPF1341](#)) (University of Melbourne 2018)

This policy covers any research undertaken with a number of subjects, including "with or about people, their *data* or tissue" (emphasis added). It supports compliance with relevant

¹³ This policy analysis was current at time of writing. The policy was under review at the time and updated 9 June 2022.

¹⁴ Note that the University of Melbourne does not have a central data repository, although this is under consideration. Open publications can be shared on the Minerva Access Platform, while open access data can be shared on Figshare. Staff and students have a range of options for storage, including School or Unit share drives as well as other options including Figshare and Minerva Access, as well as AARNET's Cloudstor. Recommendations for other repositories that may include open access data storage and sharing are also recommended on the university's 'Open Research' library guide (although it should be noted that one of the leading secure repositories with data storage and sharing capabilities, the ADA, is not listed) (Neish 2022).

Commonwealth and State legislation, codes and frameworks regarding privacy and data, including the *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research*, and the state [*Privacy and Data Protection Act 2014*](#) (Vic).

It outlines the principles of ethical human research including respecting the rights and welfare of, and minimising risk and harm to participants. Complying with this involves ethical collection and treatment of research data and dictates that researchers must

obtain the approval of a properly constituted Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) for more than low-risk research, or Human Ethics Advisory Group (HEAG) for low-risk research before human research may be undertaken. (MPF1341, 5.1(a)) [see next section, 3.2.4, for changed to this nomenclature]

This dovetails with both MPF1242 and MPF1318 in that ethical practice includes ethical and data management, including administrative retention and management of data, as well as protection and privacy of participants' data.

3.2.4 Ethics applications

Researchers engaging with human subjects at the University of Melbourne must comply with legislation and codes relating to ethics in human research as outlined in the *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research*, which links with other legislation, frameworks, policies and procedures.

As a result, researchers need to apply for ethics approval through the Office of Research Ethics and Integrity (OREI). In the policy, from 2018, the responsible committees for assessing applications are the: Human Research Ethics Committee (HREC) ('more than low-risk research') or the Human Ethics Advisory Group (HEAG) ('low-risk research') for any research involving human participants (MPF1341, 5.1(a)). However, in November 2020, these were modified to utilise the nomenclature Greater than Low Risk (GTLR), and Low and Negligible Risk (LNR) committees (University of Melbourne n.d.b).

The ethics application filled out by researchers contains a number of fields related to the governance of data. This includes the requirement to provide a Research Data Management Plan; identifying ethics research training undertaken by investigators; obtaining informed consent from participants; and the collection, disclosure and dissemination of potentially sensitive, identifiable or re-identifiable data; data storage including length of storage.

As part of the ARDC Institutional Underpinnings project discussed above, Phase 2 involves the University of Melbourne undertaking a program of work examining the ethics process (including training, policies and support) in relation to open data and data sharing.

3.2.5 Research training, policies and procedures

There is widespread presumption that an inclusive and consistent community of practice surrounds data sharing. But this is often not the case. Many researchers do not have the knowledge, support or infrastructure available to responsibly share their data. As a result, capacity building and researcher development is essential to enable researchers to share their data (Bromley & Warnock 2021).

At the University of Melbourne, research training, training policies, and procedures underpin other policies that have relevance to data governance and provide some capacity for researchers to share their data.

All university staff and students have access to the RIOT (Research Integrity Online Training), which

covers the principles of research integrity and their application to the planning, conducting and reporting of research. The content is aligned with the *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research 2018*, providing reference to the most recent policy and guidelines, as well as specific University of Melbourne policy and support links. ([University of Melbourne, n.d.c](#))

The current modules in the training include managing and recording research; and data selection, analysis and presentation. This training is compulsory for all graduate research students and must be completed prior to confirmation; it is recommended but not mandated for academic staff. It is not currently referred to in any of the research training or data management policies at the university. While this is a generic research package for university researchers, particularly research higher degree students, there are individualised examples within the training package for discipline-specific approaches to some aspects.

Continuing and fixed term staff at the University are required to complete a 45-minute online training ‘Managing Information’, which gives an overview of data management and privacy requirements, as well as the ‘Cybersecurity’ course.

For graduate researchers, the key policy is the *Graduate Research Training Policy* ([MPF1321](#)) (University of Melbourne 2022)¹⁵. The policy itself refers to data sparingly, stating that a Masters Student must “demonstrate advanced learning in research skills and mastery of appropriate techniques, such as the use of archival or primary evidence, analysis of data, judgement of conflicting evidence” (MPF1321, 4.127a). In other sections the skills of data management, including ethical practices, are suggested or implied. This is the case for PhD students who must “demonstrate a thorough grasp of the appropriate methodological techniques and an awareness of their limitations” (MPF1321, 4.126b) and “demonstrate an understanding of, and commitment to, research ethics and integrity” (MPF1321, 4.126e).

Responsible research for Graduate researchers at the university is covered off in the ‘Responsible Research’ section of the Graduate Research Hub. Graduate researchers “must appropriately record and store [their] research data” ([University of Melbourne, n.d.d](#)) and are guided to the research data management resource page on the University’s Research Gateway, a tool for all staff and students to manage their research data, including creating data management plans, organising and storing data, publishing and retaining data, and soon will provide guidelines on managing sensitive data. It ties in with the [Managing Data @Melbourne](#) (University of Melbourne n.d.c) research data management training program, developed for graduate and early career researchers, and “information professionals” but open to all students and staff.

¹⁵ This policy analysis was current at time of writing. The policy was under review at the time and updated 22 December 2022.

4 Qualitative Data & Governance

4.1 Attention to qualitative data in legislation, codes and policies

In much of the relevant legislation, as with many research and peak body codes, funding body requirements and university policies, the use of the term ‘research data’ there is usually little differentiation between qualitative and quantitative (or mixed-methods) data. This implies that the issues regarding governance of data are essentially the same (regardless of type of data) and, therefore, it arguably seems logical that a common or homogenous approach to data governance is not inappropriate, as detailed below. This section does not analyse the impact of the differentiation or lack thereof between qualitative data in these legislation, policies, codes and frameworks but analyses *if* they are differentiated between. The impact of such differentiation or lack thereof will be the subject of the final version of this report to be submitted mid-2023.

4.1.1 Commonwealth and State legislation and codes

Commonwealth and State legislation do not differentiate between qualitative and quantitative data, with all data (and privacy of information) falling under their purview. The Research Codes and associated documentation, however, have a mixed approach to differentiation of qualitative and quantitative data.

The *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research* differentiates between qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods data. Despite being the supporting guide for the *Australian Code*, the document *Management of Data and Information in Research: A Guide Supporting the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research* (NHMRC 2019), the NHMRC does not mention qualitative data specifically either. The final report that follows on from this (to be published in mid-2023) will further analyse the potential impact (or lack thereof) of this lack of differentiation in such codes.

However, the *National Statement* (NHMRC 2007/2018) provides much more detail as to the management of data and mentions qualitative data six times, indicating awareness of different types of data. Yet, there is limited differentiation between the nature of qualitative and quantitative data. Qualitative data is mentioned in terms of: definition (103); gauging risk “evidence may be qualitative or quantitative” (13); in determining risk, assessments should be based on evidence “whether qualitative or quantitative”; and the statement that human research involves wide range of practices “qualitative, quantitative or mixed”.

The statement does, however, at two points indicate that it recognises the difference in nature between qualitative and quantitative data and the richness and detailed information that might be contained in the former but does not indicate that the data should be treated any differently. In Element 1: Research Scope, Aims, Themes, Questions and Methods it states that

reviewers should be aware that some research designs will be informed and shaped by the experience, insights and/or needs of participants. Such designs can be a valid and powerful way to collect qualitative information and to inform practice. (3.1.3, 27)

It also states that “Researchers should provide participants with qualitative and, if available, quantitative information regarding the likelihood that returnable findings will be discovered” (3.3.50, 55), suggesting that descriptive summaries are the most appropriate way to impart

information to participants.

4.1.2 Funding bodies

Since 2020, the ARC's guidelines for applicants has included a requirement for a detailed data management plan be in place. The University of Melbourne, for example, provides a template for a data management plan for ARC-funded projects. These include questions regarding the type of data and records that will be collected and how they will be stored. Amongst the suggested data are classic qualitative sources, such video and audio files, photos, and culturally sensitive data, but the template does not stipulate any requirements for management of qualitative data specifically; rather, it is up to the researcher to state how they will manage their data, with standard legislative requirements. ([University of Melbourne 2022](#)).

4.1.3 Peak body guidelines and ethics

Like most legislation and codes, peak research bodies do not differentiate between qualitative and quantitative data directly nor acknowledge the need for the different treatment of these two types of data in data management or governance. However, for the four peak research associations discussed above, there would likely be an understanding that a significant proportion of data gathered could be characterised as qualitative, unstructured or as generated through mixed-methods and the use of a range of data types, and further that the sensitivities of such data require adherence to various legislation and importantly adherence to best practice protocols in the relevant research methodologies.

4.1.4 University of Melbourne frameworks, policies, guidelines & ethics clearance

In the example of the University of Melbourne above, as noted, research policies do not explicitly distinguish between qualitative and quantitative data. Applications for ethics approval, however, request details of the type of data to be collected, how it will be analysed, and the research methodology. It also directs researchers planning on using qualitative data to section 3.1 of the *National Statement*, which “discusses the manner in which the core principles of this National Statement should be reflected in the elements of research project design” (NHMRC 2018, 25–42).

4.2 Problems with lack of differentiation of qualitative and quantitative data

From this brief overview, there is little evidence of specific governance requirements relating to qualitative data in either the academic and government sectors or funding bodies. Within this there few instances where the differences between qualitative and quantitative data and the effect of these differences on data management is discussed. As McLeod and O'Connor have previously stated, ‘most ... policies tend to pay lip service to the impact of differences in how data is generated and used’ (McLeod & O'Connor, 2021).

Kirilova and Karcher note the problematic nature of lack of differentiation between qualitative and quantitative data in the realm of data management and protection of sensitive data, arguing that:

the applicability of emerging protection models from the quantitative realm must be carefully evaluated for application to the qualitative realm. At the same time, qualitative scholars already employ a variety of strategies for human-participant

protection implicitly or informally during the research process. ([Kirilova & Karcher 2017](#)).

If there are no stated governance requirements, the assumption seems to be that researchers must follow data governance at a very generic level, integrated with ethical guidelines from the field in which they operate.

This is the conclusion drawn by Kirilova and Karcher in their assessment of the Qualitative Data Archive's (QDR) protection of research participants:

QDR's current prescriptions rest on trying to maximize those of the so-called "Five Safes" (Corti and Welpton, 2015) that are and will remain most relevant for qualitative work in the social sciences. While "safe data" and "safe outputs" can rarely be produced from sensitive qualitative materials, educating researchers how to be "safe people" and how to plan for "safe projects" – when accessing such data and using them for secondary analysis – and providing long-term "safe settings" for the data, including via de-identification and appropriate access controls, will remain QDR's focus in its future work with researchers. (Kirilova & Karcher 2017, para 23)]

There are a number of guides in the social sciences for governance of qualitative data, including sharing and reuse. The most prominent is provided by Corti et al. (2014), which includes discussion of the potential of the Five Safes as an application for qualitative data. McLeod, O'Connor and Davis (2020, 11–23) have also identified a number of best practice guidelines for the sharing and re-use of qualitative data. This includes those surrounding issues of:

1. Consent and confidentiality of data.
2. Data anonymisation.
3. Setting access conditions to data.
4. Selection and preparation of data for deposit in a repository.

As noted by a number of scholars, there is a concern with the blanket application of protocols governing quantitative data to qualitative data. These will be discussed further in the interim *Implications of CADRE Platform for Qualitative Data* report, which is in preparation by the current authors.

5 GLAMR Sector Governance of Sensitive Data/Collections

5.1 Introduction

The GLAMR (Galleries, Libraries, Archives, Museums & Records) is a blanket term for a range of organisations that fall under the umbrella of the 'cultural' sector. These institutions usually hold large and diverse collections, much of which would be considered as a form of or related to qualitative data, such as visual and textual records.

Perspectives and practices from the sector can be of interest to and influence wider data curation and governance practices, including for qualitative, quantitative and mixed-mode research in HASS and beyond (McLeod 2017).

5.2 Types of GLAMR institutions

GLAMR organisations exist both within government, university, and non-government contexts. They are all beholden to some legislation, government policy, codes of conduct, and ethical frameworks. Guidelines and policies can differ immensely for individual organisations depending on their context and funding. Government-run institutions, for example, are usually subject to overarching federal, state and municipal policies on data governance, while they might have individual policies that operate under this.

- *Government/publicly funded*

Federal, State and Municipal levels all have cultural institutions, including archival repositories, that fall under the GLAMR sector. Examples of these include:

- Commonwealth/Federal: National Archives of Australia (which also has branches in each state and the Northern Territory), National Museum of Australia, National Gallery of Australia, National Library of Australia.

Each of these as Commonwealth public sector data holders must comply with all Commonwealth legislation that applies to both data protection and records management/governance.

- State: Art Gallery NSW, Museums Victoria, Public Records Office Victoria.

These must adhere to relevant state and Commonwealth legislation, public sector governance frameworks and industry codes and policies.

- *University Collections*

Publicly funded universities also have such divisions (e.g., University of Melbourne Archives, Chau Chak Wing Museum at University of Sydney) and, while governed by relevant Commonwealth and state legislation, also have their own policies – including university policies and their own specific individual policies, as well as industry ethical frameworks.

- *Private GLAMR Organisations*

There are also numerous private GLAMR institutions in Australia (e.g, MONA Hobart). These are governed by relevant state and Commonwealth legislation, industry frameworks and their own policies.

5.3 Qualitative data in GLAMR organisations

GLAMR institutions hold a large amount of data and collections, many of which might be characterised as qualitative data or related to qualitative data. These include both material culture objects or analogue data but also significant (and increasing) amounts of born-digital and digitised data. Qualitative data in GLAMR Organisations are diverse and numerous. There is also often overlap in the types of material held. Museums might hold archival documents, while archives hold ephemera and material cultural collections, libraries might have archival repositories, storing a wide range of material including photographs, plans,

business minutes, interviews and more. As institutions that often do research (either for their own exhibitions and collections or in conjunction with academics, tertiary institutions, and government organisations), they hold extensive qualitative data on individuals, groups, communities and locations; these might also be considered as part of material culture/collections.

There are some important differences between these types of institutions, despite any intersecting purposes and collections. State and national archives, for instance, usually have a legislative responsibility for recordkeeping and the retention of government records as well as establishing or contributing to that legislation and the governance of recordkeeping in various government organisations. The *State Records Act 1998* (New South Wales) among other provisions, places responsibility for archiving, retention, recovery and disposal of, as well as public access to, State records in the hands of the NSW State Archives and Records Authority. It defines the Authority's powers and responsibilities, including developing and monitoring records management standards and codes of best practice for NSW public offices ([NSW State Archives & Records, 2014/2018](#)).

For the purposes of this short report, some examples of qualitative data across several types of GLAMR institutions are provided. The focus here is predominantly on online collections with the data more open to a global audience, using some specific examples of Australian institutions to illustrate. While these are large institutions, their areas of collection also reflect those of many others down to small community collections.

Museums have large collections of material culture that might also be considered or intersect with qualitative data. The Museums Victoria Collections Online, fully available to the public, holds over [112,000 items](#) (“things made and used by people”) with a diverse array of photographs, diaries, books, pamphlets, maps, plans, oral histories, scrapbooks, banners and many other objects that would be considered or contain rich qualitative data. There are also [2,230 Articles](#) that provide detailed stories of “people, places, events and [the] collections” ([MV n.d.b](#)). Further qualitative information is also held in the museums' collection management database from which this online metadata is drawn but the full extent of which is not available to the public.

Libraries hold similar collections. Theirs are in the majority paper-based but they also collect ephemera (collection objects) relevant to areas of study. The National Library of Australia for example holds books, pictures, music, journals, microforms, manuscripts, audio and video recordings, newspapers and more. In its online catalogue, a majority of e-resources are drawn from various databases but it also includes over [350,000 digitised items](#) from the library's own collection (NLA n.d.a).

The Public Records Office Victoria “is the **archive** of the State and local government in Victoria. ... [It] hold[s] around 100kms of hard copy records and 600,000 digital records dating from 1836 to the present day” ([PROV](#), n.d.a). Like the museums and libraries, they hold large collections of qualitative data, such as images, maps, plans, government documents such as inquests, city council minutes, court, bankruptcy, land, immigration, hospital, asylum, and Indigenous records, and many more. They have the further function of being responsible for “set[ting] mandatory recordkeeping standards and provid[ing] support and advice on recordkeeping to state and local government.” ([PROV](#), n.d.a).

Galleries likewise hold mainly art-based collections ranging from drawings to paintings to photographs but all of which might have large amounts of qualitative data and metadata about people attached to them. Like other institutions, they also hold other items such as video and audio recordings (such as oral histories of artists), manuscripts, and other materials relating to their collections. Art Gallery NSW has over [35,000 works](#), and 235 artist profiles in their online collection, sometimes with detailed qualitative data (AGNSW n.d.a).

Online GLAMR collection items also often have detailed metadata attached to them, which reveals information about people, places, groups, and communities. They also often conduct detailed [provenance](#) (AGNSW n.d.b) research and research for understanding and exhibiting their collection items. Through this process they might collect significant qualitative data, such as information about individual lives (an artist or owner of an object), communities and groups, and stories about them, which are then held by the institution (although not necessarily publicly available). Each of these institutions explores their collections and stories about people, groups, communities, and places through online engagement, including sometimes detailed descriptions of the collection item, including through blog posts, journals, information sheets/pages, and their websites more broadly. In combination, this reveals large volumes of diverse qualitative data about individuals, communities, groups, and places online to a wide audience.

5.4 GLAMR institutions and governance of data/collection management

As noted, GLAMR institutions must follow relevant federal and state laws governing data, but they also operate under a range of codes and guidelines established by various peak bodies. The peak body for the sector overall is GLAM Peak, which

brings together the representative bodies for Australia's galleries, libraries, archives, museums, historical societies, cultural heritage organisations and research peak bodies. Its members have been working together since 2015 to expand digital access to Australian community heritage collections ... ([GLAMPeak, n.d.](#))

GLAMR peak bodies in Australia include both national and state-based organisations (government and non-government), which usually operate in conjunction with or under the national body. These include:

- [Australian Library and Information Association](#) (ALIA)
- [Australian Museums and Galleries Association](#) (AMAGA)
- [Australian Society of Archivists](#) (ASA)
- [Federation of Australian Historical Societies](#) (FAHS)
- [International Council of Museums Australia](#) (ICOM)
- [University Art Museums Australia](#) (UAMA)

Members (which might be individual or institutional) must follow the peak body codes of ethics, as well as international frameworks, guidelines, and federal and state legislation relevant to the cultural sector. This includes the [Museums Australia Code of Ethics \(1999\)](#), which builds on the ICOM (International Council of Museum) Statutes of 1974 ([MA 1999](#)) and the [ICOM Code of Ethics for Museums \(2017\)](#), while the *National Standards for Australian Museums and Galleries (2016)* is a guide to best practice in museums and galleries.

In many cases, these include the governance of data, a large amount of which would be qualitative or unstructured in nature. The data itself might be generated in diverse ways, including qualitative research, crowdsourcing, organisational recordkeeping and more that might be differentiated from numerical or ‘big data’. In the GLAMR sector, ‘qualitative data’ would more likely be referred to as ‘collections’ and considered distinct from other sensitive or other data held by these organisations (e.g., mailing lists, statistical data on visitation, etc.).

In this regard, it is best practice and usually required by peak bodies at GLAMR organisations to have “formal, written policies and procedures that cover [their] management, responsibilities, programs and services” (*National Standard*, 23–24). An essential component of these is a collection management plan or policy. A cultural institution’s collection management policy might include a range of other policies that relate to the governance of their collections and other data, including conservation, access, information management, privacy, and research policies. Each institution is different, and the range and detail of these policies might depend on aspects such as its size and whether it is a government- or university-run or independent organisation.

These standards, ethical frameworks and collection policies not only include procedures and politics for open data and online sharing of data, including collection items and metadata, which will be discussed further in 5.4 below after the following brief examination on how and why GLAMR organisation are facilitating access to their collections more than ever before.

5.5 Facilitating open access to cultural collections

In the last decade, GLAMR organisations, particularly those that are publicly funded, have increasingly seen the benefit in making their collections and research more open and available to the wider community. This is through the digitisation of objects/items and their display in freely accessible online collections, together with other online initiatives such as websites, blog posts and detailed contextual information about specific items, collections, people, places, groups and communities.

Global heritage and museum bodies have in the last decades mandated or suggested open access policy frameworks to their member organisations. The emphasis on greater access to museum collections has been associated with other movements such as history from below, changes in oral history practices and the emphasis on history as a domain for social change, as well as the broader democratisation of history over the past forty to fifty years. Reflecting on her experience of working with the Archives of Lesbian Oral Testimony (A LOT), Elise Chenier (2014) writes:

The digital humanities and the open access movement ... might well be the natural offspring of the 1970s oral history movement. ... the activist oriented, community-based practice of oral history that emerged in the early 1970s [, which] ... aimed to counter formal, elite knowledge with organic knowledge – to break through the walls of academe and the scholarly world, to legitimate and create a place and space for the knowledge that arises from everyday experience. In so doing, the oral history movement democratized knowledge and empowered citizens. The relationship oral history shares with digital humanities is obvious: both make ‘data’ accessible to broad publics, both encourage and facilitate people to become ‘content creators’, not passive consumers, and both regard these practices as having transformative potential.

As Noehrer et al. (2021) have noted, due to lockdowns precipitated by the COVID-19 pandemic, going online also meant survival for many cultural institutions, but this experience also brought into sharp relief the human labour and monetary cost associated with getting collections online. Although further research on the effects of these changes is needed, it likely increased conversations and awareness about the sensitive nature of much of the data held by cultural institutions.

5.5.1 Facilitating access to collections: digitisation, open and online

For these museums and collecting institution, greater access facilitates a wider interest in and engagement with their collections and going online is part of broader strategies and policies to reach out to the wider community. This contrasts with a more traditional approach that relies on visitors physically attending cultural institutions or a small group of curators and researchers holding the information for their own use. And, more practically, GLAMR organisations have large collections with only a fraction able to be physically displayed at one time.

Institutional policies and missions are providing greater and wide access to their collections as part of their collection management plans. For PROV, this is reflected in its statement on Open Data:

Public Record Office Victoria is committed to ensuring that its archival collection is discoverable and accessible to as many people as possible. One of the ways PROV does this is by making information (metadata) about the vast quantity of physical records in its collection easily available to researchers through different online sites and channels (PROV, n.d.b)

For Museums Victoria commitment to open data, greater access to and engagement with the collections is a vital part of its *Strategic Plan 2017–2025*. A main ‘Transformational Theme’ is to “Develop a Digital Life for Museums Victoria that takes the wonder and inspiration of our collections, knowledge and expertise beyond our walls through audience-centred experiences that connect with hearts and minds” (MV 2020, 7) . This underpins its Vision of “People enriched by wondrous discovery and trusted knowledge”, which is delivered in part by through its digital platforms (MV, n.d.c, 6).

This includes the museum’s significant Collections Online platform (which was initially developed in [early 2010?]). Access, sharing and reuse of content is encouraged and partly facilitated by the application of a Creative Commons licence to images, audio and video material (over 100,000 items) where possible and all information created by curators, collection managers and other staff (MV n.d.a), the creation of an API that allows researchers, developers and others to agglomerate data through the Collections Online. The museum’s website code is also freely available through GitHub.

Many collection items are also fragile and easily damaged or may have a shortened life through regular use or display. Digitising is therefore not only an engagement strategy but also a significant preventive conservation measure, with the two concerns intertwined.

The National Library of Australia states with regard to its preservation framework:

A fundamental role of the National Library is to preserve Australia's documentary heritage, and to make sure it is available for people to use for as long as possible. Collecting material is only one step towards achieving this - the material also needs to be looked after if it is to remain useable. ([NLA, n.d.b](#))

It sees digitisation and online collections as an integral part of this ([NLA, n.d.c](#)).

For AIATSIS (Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies), “by digitising, we can preserve the original collection item as it was deposited and also allow it to be accessible to more people”, including the diverse Indigenous communities, as well as other clients and visitors across a geographically diverse area that wish to access collection items ([AIATSIS n.d.](#)). Their “digitisation program is guided by [the] Collections Business Plan and is undertaken in line with the Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Library, Information and Resource Network (ATSILIRN) protocols. [They] also follow the IASA Guidelines and operate in accordance with the Australian Institute of Cultural Materials (AICCM) Code of Ethics and Code of Practice.”

Others are increasingly digitising their oral history collections and providing online access to increase public access and engagement. “Some of these include: The State Library of Western Australia; the National Library of Australia; City of Sydney Archives; and the Museum of Australian Democracy” (McLeod 2017). Archives and libraries are also expending enormous effort in digitising their materials and either placing them online or providing metadata and information online that assists with locating the information and access.

One of the most well-known and largest projects to facilitate access to collections in Australia is the National Library of Australia’s *Trove* website, which has facilitated digitisation of millions of Australian newspapers and made them, unlike some international repositories, available for free online. It is best known for these newspaper archives, but it is also a powerful platform for searching collection items, including images, from GLAMR institutions Australia wide, in addition to government gazettes and archived websites.

The platform harvests metadata from participating institutions and displays it (often including a thumbnail image), making it easily searchable. This is a model, which has considerable synchronicity with the CADRE platform, which will also similarly harvest metadata from the institutions and organisations that participate and direct researchers to the data collections on these organisations’ websites. The platform has been an overwhelming success due to significant support of and buy in from the cultural community as well as the broader public. It is a key resource for wide varieties of research and, when threatened by Federal budget cuts, the uproar ensured its ongoing (for now) support ([Jones & Verhoeven 2016](#); [Stainforth 2018](#)).

5.6 Open data, online collections and governance in GLAMR organisations

Digitisation of collections and open access/science strategies are actively encouraged and supported by most GLAMR governing bodies and other relevant institutions.

UNESCO’s Recommendation on Open Science includes encouragement for open access of data in GLAMR and heritage organisations, enumerating the great potential of open science, including to open up opportunities for open science to “foster knowledge ... and [narrow] ... inequalities [as well as] ... [providing] more open, transparent, collaborative and inclusive scientific processes” ([UNESCO 2021](#)). It also sees museums, including virtual museums, as

playing “fundamental roles in education and research” ([UNESCO n.d.b](#)) and as essential to intercultural dialogue, [as well as other important functions \(UNESCO n.d.a\)](#).

Furthermore, in 2003, UNESCO released its Charter on the Preservation of Digital Heritage, which stated that “access to this heritage will offer broadened opportunities for creation, communication and sharing of knowledge among all peoples” and aimed to foster and support digital heritage preservation ([UNESCO 2003](#)). Shaw notes that as a result, “The National Library of Australia prepared a ‘How to’ guide – Guidelines for the Preservation of Digital Heritage – as a companion to the UNESCO Charter. It provides practical information and principles on the management of digital heritage material through its lifecycle” ([Shaw 2011](#), 3)

GLAMR Peak, the peak body for peak body organisations in Australia also encourages digitisation and open data. In 2016 it released the Digital Access to Collections project report, which assessed barriers and enablers to bringing collections online both for smaller and larger institutions ([GLAM Peak 2016](#)). It also created a framework and toolkit to enable staff to digitise and provide access to their collections ([MGNSW n.d.](#))

Individual peak bodies also support digitisation of and online access to collections through both policies and on-the-ground support. The Australian Society of Archivists, for example, is a member of “the Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC). Through our membership of the DPC we have the opportunity to shape the program of digital preservation support which we can make available to meet ASA members’ needs, and to participate in international discussions on best-practice digital preservation.” ([ASA, n.d.a](#)). The DPC, whose members include a large number of international institutions and government record keepers, including ASA, NLA, AIATSIS, and University of Sydney Library, “enable[s] ... members to deliver resilient long-term access to digital content and services, helping them to derive enduring value from digital assets” ([DPC, n.d.](#))

ICOM, AMAGA (Australian Museums & Galleries Association), MGNSW (Museums & Galleries NSW) are other bodies that encourage and facilitate digitisation for their members.

5.7 Ethics/privacy/sensitive data

Like other research institutions, GLAMR organisations must follow government laws and Codes on data and privacy, and they often subscribe to broader ethical and integrity frameworks, such as the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research. They are also beholden to national and international copyright laws when reproducing images and other material as a third party and must follow industry guidelines and ethical frameworks on collections management.

Some of the same concerns about ethics that we see in research discussions of qualitative data also arise in the cultural field. In the GLAM Peak report *Digital Access to Collections*, many ([2020](#)) summarised some of the ethical issues in the digitisation of heritage, including:

- the potential for Indigenous communities to regain control over cultural knowledge but the concomitant hazards of this being beholden to Western cultural normative frameworks and potential appropriation of this knowledge by others (3–6).

- labour and monetary costs associated with preparation of materials for digitisation and online presentation (6–7)
- potential manipulation of digital content and misuse through sharing (7–12)

Others have identified the complications of understanding and ascribing copyright to collection items when a GLAMR organisation is presenting the material of third parties, legal risk to institutions presenting this material online and the risk for artists and makers of content itself (Hudson & Kenyon 2007; Bandle et al. 2020). Extension of the *Copyright Act 1968* with the proposed [Copyright Amendment \(Access Reform\) Bill](#), allows organisations to have greater flexibility to release copyrighted materials to be used in a digital environment, increasing public access and equitable provision of those materials, but may increase risk for copyright holders to some extent (Commonwealth of Australia 2021, 22).

Peter Shaw, from the National Library of Australia, identified key challenges surrounding context and materiality in a 2011 paper on digitisation of images. He argued that “a major challenge for digitisation is to ensure that the final viewed image [or object] authentically reproduces the creators’ intent” (Shaw 2011, 3) and, moreover, that the lack of materiality renders the viewing experience online as very different to that generated by viewing an object or item *in situ*. He posits that this can be overcome to an extent by capturing any detailed information left by the creator and/or ensuring the reproduction is as faithful to the original as possible. Over the last decade this has become easier by the increasing use of techniques such as 3D photogrammetry to capture items.

Other intersecting concerns that are, however, little discussed in relation to digitisation and release of cultural collections are those of privacy, ethics and the sensitivity of information. This has recently become a topic of greater interest, partially spurred on by the increased access to information about individuals, communities and groups through online collections, such as in online museums and archives and family history aggregate sites such as Ancestry. Using the example of inquests, May et al. (2020) discussed this predicament in historical research, which extends to online presentation of sensitive data. Inquest records, which were created with government recordkeeping, at their heart contain rich detail about past lives, including details that are sometimes traumatic in nature.

The archive of the coroner’s inquest, in other words, sits within competing imperatives of open and transparent justice on the one hand, and personal sensitivity and private trauma on the other.

[It] reveal[s] a moral purpose and ethical responsibility ... , both in seeking the voice of victims ... and in ensuring that we remain attuned to the agency of the individual and the actualities of their existence ...

as Holly Crossen-White [2015] cautions, the availability of online digital archives shines a light onto a level of detail about our forebears that they [or their ancestors] may not wish to have illuminated. ... The historian’s opportunity—indeed, we might say, duty—is, thus, to be responsible to the people of our past (May et al. 2020)

Such epistemological work that questions how we address sensitive data, even in historic documents, likewise speaks to such concerns in wider research contexts and with other data where more open access is being championed.

From the GLAMR sector, we may be able to adopt practises that facilitate public and researcher access to qualitative data in other fields, including the social sciences. This however, at the same time, requires the maintenance of ethical frameworks and considerations that apply to differing levels of sensitivity of data in specific fields.

6 Conclusion

This report is the first iteration of an analysis of the governance and management of qualitative and unstructured data across a number of sectors. A final report will be produced and submitted in 2023 at the completion of the CADRE project. This report was primarily concerned with research data in the tertiary sector, bookended by relevant legislation and practice in government and cultural contexts. It is intended as an examination that can contribute to informed consideration of ethical and methodological concerns surrounding the storage, archiving, access and re-use of qualitative data, particularly its management, sharing and reuse, but can also be extended out to thinking about other types of data.

While we must remain aware of the special needs and sensitivities of qualitative data, consideration of this type of data and its richness and detail also highlights the need for proper governance of all types of data and the information that can be mined from it. Research data is diverse, and we must attend to the possibilities that it holds but also be cognisant of the sensitivities surrounding it and the details that it might reveal about individuals, groups and communities.

References

- Art Gallery NSW (AGNSW) (n.d.a). *Collection*.
<https://www.artgallery.nsw.gov.au/collection/>
- Art Gallery NSW (AGNSW) (n.d.b). *Provenance*.
<https://www.artgallery.nsw.gov.au/art/collection/provenance/>
- Attorney-General's Department (n.d.). *Protective Security Policy Framework: Policies*.
<https://www.protectivesecurity.gov.au/policies>
- Australian Association for Research in Education (AARE) (n.d.). *AARE Code of Ethics*.
<https://www.aare.edu.au/assets/documents/policies/AARE-Code-of-Ethics.pdf>
- ADA [Australian Data Archive] Dataverse (n.d.). *The Australian Longitudinal Study on Male Health Dataverse*. <https://dataverse.ada.edu.au/dataverse/tentomen>
- Australian Historical Association (AHA) (n.d.). *AHA Code of Ethics*.
<https://theaha.org.au/about-the-aha/aha-code-of-ethics/>
- Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (AIATSIS) (2020). *AIATSIS Code of Ethics for Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Research*.
<https://aiatsis.gov.au/sites/default/files/2020-10/aiatsis-code-ethics.pdf>
- Australian Institute of Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Studies (AIATSIS) (n.d.). *Caring for the Collection*. <https://aiatsis.gov.au/collection/caring-collection>
- Australian Institute of Health & Welfare (AIHW) (2021). *Data Governance Framework 2021 (Public Edition)*. <https://www.aihw.gov.au/getmedia/c3e00f60-c40d-4989-ad22-de1be3ab5380/Data-Governance-Framework-2021.pdf.aspx>
- Australian Research Council (ARC) (n.d.a). *Codes and Guidelines*.
<https://www.arc.gov.au/policies-strategies/policy/codes-and-guidelines>
- Australian Research Council (ARC) (2019). *Research Data Management*.
<https://www.arc.gov.au/policies-strategies/strategy/research-data-management>
- Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) (n.d.). *Institutional Underpinnings*.
<https://ardc.edu.au/collaborations/strategic-activities/national-data-assets/institutional-underpinnings/>
- Australian Society of Archivists (n.d.). *Digital Archives*.
<https://www.archivists.org.au/community/digital-archives>
- Bandle, Anne Laure; Benhamou, Yaniv; Burkhalter, Sarah; Ferland, Justine; Guibault, Lucie; Heaton, Mathilde; Logeais, Elisabeth; Renold, Marc-André; Sykora, Sandra; & Vuille, Vanessa (2020). *Policy Paper on the Digitization of Museum Collections*.
<https://www.digitizationpolicies.com/medias/Policy-Paper-on-Digitization-of-Collections.pdf>

Bromley, Tony & Warnock, Lorna (2021). The Practice of the Development of Researchers: the “State-of-the-art”, *Studies in Graduate and Postdoctoral Education* 12(2). ISSN: 2398-4686. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/SGPE-12-2019-0084/full/html>

Chenier, Elise (2014). ‘Oral History and Open Access: Fulfilling the Promise of Democratizing Knowledge’, *New American Notes Online*, Issue 5: Digital Humanities, Public Humanities. <https://nanocrit.com/issues/issue5/oral-history-and-open-access-fulfilling-promise-democratizing-knowledge>

Commonwealth of Australia, Department of Infrastructure, Transport, Regional Development & Communications (2021). ‘Discussion paper—Exposure Draft *Copyright Amendment (Access Reform) Bill 2021* & Review of Technological Protection Measures Exceptions’. <https://www.infrastructure.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/discussion-paper--exposure-draft-copyright-amendment--access-reform--bill2021.pdf>

Coordinated Access for Data, Research and Environments (CADRE) (2022). *CADRE Five Safes Framework v.1.0.1* [Draft]. [10.5281/zenodo.5748610](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5748610)

Crossen-White, Holly (2015). ‘Using Digital Archives in Historical Research: What Are the Ethical Concerns for a ‘Forgotten’ Individual?’ *Research Ethics* 11(2): 108–119. DOI:[10.1177/1747016115581724](https://doi.org/10.1177/1747016115581724)

Data.NSW (2020). *Data Sharing Principles*. <https://data.nsw.gov.au/data-sharing-principles>

Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet (2019). *Best Practice Guide to Applying Data Sharing Principles*. <https://www.datacommissioner.gov.au/sites/default/files/2019-08/data-sharing-principles-best-practice-guide-15-mar-2019.pdf>

Department of Prime Minister and Cabinet (n.d.). *New Laws to Improve Access to Data and Use of Data: A Data Sharing and Release Legislative Package*. <https://dataavailability.pmc.gov.au/new-laws-improve-access-data-use.html>

Desai, Tanvi, Ritchie, Felix, Ritchie & Welpton, Richard (2016). *Five Safes: Designing Data Access for Research*. Economics Working Papers in Economics, No. 1601. University of the West of England, Bristol. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.1.3661.1604; <https://www2.uwe.ac.uk/faculties/bbs/Documents/1601.pdf>

Digital Preservation Coalition (n.d.). *About*. <https://www.dpconline.org/about>

GLAMPeak (2016). *Digital Access to Collections: Stage 1 Project Report*. <https://apo.org.au/sites/default/files/resource-files/2016-12/apo-nid76281.pdf>

GLAMPeak (n.d.). <https://glampeak.org.au/>

Government of South Australia, Department of Premier and Cabinet (n.d.). *Sharing Public Sector Data*. <https://www.dpc.sa.gov.au/responsibilities/data-sharing/information-sharing-in-south-australia/sharing-public-sector-data>

Government of Victoria (n.d.). *Navigating Legislation and Sharing Safely*. <https://www.vic.gov.au/navigating-legislation-sharing-safely>

Group of Eight (n.d.). *About the Go8*. <https://go8.edu.au/about/the-go8>
Intergovernmental Agreement on Data Sharing between Commonwealth and State and Territory Governments (2021).
<https://federation.gov.au/sites/default/files/about/agreements/iga-on-data-sharing-signed.pdf>

Health Direct (n.d.) *NHMRC – National Health and Medical Research Council*.
<https://www.healthdirect.gov.au/partners/nhmrc-national-health-and-medical-research-council>

Hudson, Emily & Kenyon, Andrew T. (2007). ‘Digital Access: The Impact of Copyright on Digitization Practices in Australian Museums, Galleries, Libraries and Archives’, *The University of New South Wales Law Journal* 30(1): 12–52.

International Council of Museums (ICOM) (2017). *ICOM Code of Ethics for Museums*.
<https://icom.museum/wp-content/uploads/2018/07/ICOM-code-En-web.pdf>

Jennerich, Ann L. (2021). ‘Unplanned Admission to the ICU: A Qualitative Study Examining Family Member Experiences’. *Qualitative Data Repository*. <https://doi.org/10.5064/F6GXXBVD>. Palliative Care Research Cooperative QDR-EOLPC . V1

Jones, Mike & Verhoeven, Deb (2016). ‘Treasure Trove: Why Defunding Trove Leaves Australia Poorer’, *The Conversation*, 26 February. <https://theconversation.com/treasure-trove-why-defunding-trove-leaves-australia-poorer-55217>

Kirolova, Dessu & Karcher, Sebastian (2017). ‘Rethinking Data Sharing and Human Participant Protection in Social Science Research: Applications from the Qualitative Realm’, *Data Science Journal* 16(43). DOI: [10.5334/dsj-2017-043](https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2017-043)

Manžuch, Zinaida (2017). ‘Ethical Issues in Digitization Of Cultural Heritage’, *Journal of Contemporary Archival Studies* 4(2): Article 4.
<http://elischolar.library.yale.edu/jcas/vol4/iss2/4>

May, Andrew J.; Morgan, Helen; Davis, Nicole; Silberberg, Sue; Wettenhall, Roland (2020). ‘Untimely Ends: Place, Kin and Culture in Colonial Inquests’, *Provenance: The Journal of Public Record Office Victoria* 18. <https://prov.vic.gov.au/explore-collection/provenance-journal/provenance-2020/untimely-ends>

McLeod, Julie (2017). ‘Social science archives and lessons from history: a view from Australia on research governance and practices in the age of data sharing’. *Re-visioning the Regulation of Data Archiving and Sharing in the Social Sciences*, Linköping University, Sweden, 23–24 March.

McLeod, Julie, O’Connor, Kate & Davis, Nicole (2020). *Doing Research Differently: Archiving & Sharing Qualitative Data in Studies of Childhood, Education and Youth*. University of Melbourne. DOI: [10.25916/5e9e28eec21a1](https://doi.org/10.25916/5e9e28eec21a1)

McLeod, Julie & O'Connor, Kate (2020). 'Ethics, Archives and Data Sharing in Qualitative Research', *Educational Philosophy & Theory* 53(5).
<https://doi.org/10.1080/00131857.2020.1805310>

Museums & Galleries NSW (MGNSW) (n.d). *Digital Access to Collections Toolkit*.
<https://mgnsw.org.au/sector/resources/online-resources/digital/digital-access-collections-toolkit/>

Museums Australia (1999). *Museums Australia Code of Ethics (1999)*.
https://www.amaga.org.au/sites/default/files/uploaded-content/website-content/SubmissionsPolicies/ma_code_of_ethics_1999.pdf

Museums Victoria (2020). *Strategic Plan: 2017–2025*.
https://museumsvictoria.com.au/media/6663/museumsvictoria_strategicplan_2017-2025_accessible.pdf

Museums Victoria (MV) (n.d.a). *About [Museum Victoria Collections]*.
<https://collections.museumsvictoria.com.au/about>

Museums Victoria (MV) (n.d.b). *Museum Victoria Collections*.
<https://collections.museumsvictoria.com.au/>

National Archives of Australia (NAA) (2021). *Information and Data Governance Framework*. <https://www.naa.gov.au/about-us/our-organisation/accountability-and-reporting/information-and-data-governance-framework>

National Archives of Australia (NAA) (n.d.). *Information Management Standard for Australian Government*. <https://www.naa.gov.au/information-management/information-management-standards/information-management-standard-australian-government>

National Health and Medical Research Council Act 1992 (Cmwltth).
<https://www.legislation.gov.au/Details/C2014C00364>

National Health and Medical Research Council (n.d.). *Legislative Basis to NHMRC*.
<https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/leadership-and-governance/legislative-basis-nhmrc>

National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council and Universities Australia (NHMRC) (2007/2018). *National Statement on Ethical Conduct in Human Research (2007)*. <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/national-statement-ethical-conduct-human-research-2007-updated-2018>

National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council and Universities Australia (NHMRC) (2018). *Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research*. <https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/about-us/publications/australian-code-responsible-conduct-research-2018>

National Health and Medical Research Council, Australian Research Council and Universities Australia. (2019). *Management of Data and Information in Research: A Guide Supporting the Australian Code for the Responsible Conduct of Research*.

<https://www.nhmrc.gov.au/sites/default/files/documents/attachments/Management-of-Data-and-Information-in-Research.pdf>

National Library of Australia (n.d.a). *Catalogue*.

https://catalogue.nla.gov.au/Search/Home?lookfor=&filter%5b%5d=access_type:%22NLA%20digital%20material%22

National Library of Australia (n.d.b). *Preservation*.

<https://www.nla.gov.au/collections/preserving-our-collections/preservation>

National Library of Australia (n.d.c). *Preserving Our Collections*.

<https://www.nla.gov.au/content/preserving-our-collections>

National Standards for Australian Museums and Galleries (2016).

https://www.amaga.org.au/sites/default/files/uploaded-content/field_f_content_file/nsfamg_v1.5_2016.pdf

Neish, Peter (8 February 2022). 'Open Research', *Library Guides, University of Melbourne*.

<https://unimelb.libguides.com/openresearch/data>

New South Wales Government (2021). *Data.NSW*. <https://data.nsw.gov.au/>

NSW State Archives & Records (2014/2018). *Summary of Provisions*.

<https://www.records.nsw.gov.au/recordkeeping/rules/legislation/summary-of-provisions>

Office of the Australian Information Commissioner (OAIC 2019). *Australian Privacy Principles Guidelines: Privacy Act 1988*.

https://www.oaic.gov.au/_data/assets/pdf_file/0009/1125/app-guidelines-july-2019.pdf

Office of the Australian Information Commissioner (OAIC n.d.). *The Privacy Act*.

<https://www.oaic.gov.au/privacy/the-privacy-act>

Office of the National Data Commissioner (ONDC n.d.). *Our Purpose*.

<https://datacommissioner.gov.au/about/our-purpose>

Oral History Australia (OHA) (2007). *Guidelines of Ethical Practice*.

https://oralhistoryaustralia.org.au/wp-content/uploads/Guide_ethical_practice_2007.pdf

OHA (n.d.a). *Guidance*. <https://oralhistoryaustralia.org.au/guidance/>

OHA (n.d.b). *Practising Oral History*. <https://oralhistoryaustralia.org.au/guidance/practise/>

OHA (n.d.c). *University Ethical Approval of a Project involving Humans*.

<https://oralhistoryaustralia.org.au/advice-ethics-and-university-research/> [dead link, last accessed April 2022].

Organisation for Economic Co-Operation and Development (OECD) (2007). *OECD Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding*.

<https://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/38500813.pdf>

- Parliament of Australia (2020). *Data Availability and Transparency Bill 2020*. https://parlinfo.aph.gov.au/parlInfo/download/legislation/bills/r6649_first-reps/toc_pdf/20174b01.pdf;fileType=application%2Fpdf
- Parliament of Australia (n.d.). *Data Availability and Transparency Bill 2020*. https://www.aph.gov.au/Parliamentary_Business/Bills_Legislation/Bills_Search_Results/Result?bId=r6649
- Productivity Commission (2017). *Data Availability and Use: Productivity Commission Inquiry Report*. <https://www.pc.gov.au/inquiries/completed/data-access/report/data-access.pdf>
- Productivity Commission (n.d.). *Data Availability and Use*. <https://www.pc.gov.au/inquiries/completed/data-access#report>
- Public Record Office Victoria (n.d.a). *About Us*. <https://prov.vic.gov.au/about-us>
- Public Record Office Victoria (n.d.b). *Open Data*. <https://prov.vic.gov.au/about-us/partnerships-and-collaborations/open-data>
- Public Sector (Data Sharing) Act 2016* (South Australia). [https://www.legislation.sa.gov.au/LZ/C/A/PUBLIC%20SECTOR%20\(DATA%20SHARING\)%20ACT%202016.aspx](https://www.legislation.sa.gov.au/LZ/C/A/PUBLIC%20SECTOR%20(DATA%20SHARING)%20ACT%202016.aspx)
- Qualitative Data Repository (QDR) (n.d.a). *QDR Main Collection*. <https://data.qdr.syr.edu/>
- Qualitative Data Repository (QDR) (n.d.b). *Types of Qualitative Data*. <https://qdr.syr.edu/deposit/data>
- Shaw, Peter (2011). ‘Conservators and Digitisation: When we Conserve the Window, How Should We Preserve the View?’, AICCM National Conference, Canberra, 19–21 October 2011. https://aiccm.org.au/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/SHAW_NatConf2011.pdf
- Stainforth, Liz (2018). ‘Treasuring Trove: Why Australia’s Digital Heritage Platform is So Special’, *Pursuit*, 26 October. <https://pursuit.unimelb.edu.au/articles/treasuring-trove-why-australia-s-digital-heritage-platform-is-so-special>
- The Australian Sociological Association (TASA) (n.d.). *Code of Ethics*. https://www.tasa.org.au/content.aspx?page_id=22&club_id=671860&module_id=357739
- Ten to Men. The Australian Longitudinal Study on Male Health (2022). *About the Study*. <https://tentomen.org.au/about-study>
- UNESCO (2003). *Charter on the Preservation of Digital Heritage*. http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=17721&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
- UNESCO (2021). *UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000379949.locale=en>

UNESCO (n.d.a). *Museums*. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/museums>

UNESCO (n.d.b). *Museums for Intercultural Dialogue*.
<http://www.unesco.org/culture/museum-for-dialogue/museums-for-intercultural-dialog/en/>

University of Melbourne (2013). *Management of Research Data and Records Policy* (MPF1242). <https://policy.unimelb.edu.au/MPF1242>

University of Melbourne (2018). *Research Ethics and Biorisk Management Policy* (MPF1341). <https://policy.unimelb.edu.au/MPF1341>

University of Melbourne (2020a). *Australian Research Council Data Management Template 2021*. https://dmp.research.unimelb.edu.au/template_export/881326015.pdf

University of Melbourne (2020b). *Research Integrity and Misconduct Policy* (MPF1318).
<https://policy.unimelb.edu.au/MPF1318>

University of Melbourne (2022). *Graduate Research Training Policy* (MPF1321).
<https://policy.unimelb.edu.au/MPF1321>

University of Melbourne (n.d.a). *Research Data Management*.
<https://gateway.research.unimelb.edu.au/resources/data-and-computation/research-data-management> [only accessible to University of Melbourne staff, students and affiliates].

University of Melbourne (n.d.b) *Research Ethics Advisors and Human Research Ethics Committees*. <https://gateway.research.unimelb.edu.au/resources/ethics-and-integrity/human-ethics/rea-and-hrec> [only accessible to University of Melbourne staff, students and affiliates].

University of Melbourne (n.d.c). *Research Integrity Online Training*.
<https://catalog.lms.unimelb.edu.au/browse/communities/courses/research-integrity-online-training-riot> [only accessible to University of Melbourne staff, students and affiliates]

University of Melbourne (n.d.d). *Responsible Research*.
<https://gradresearch.unimelb.edu.au/roles-and-responsibilities/responsible-research>

University of Newcastle (2017). *Information Security Data Classification Procedure*.
<https://policies.newcastle.edu.au/document/view-current.php?id=256&version=1>

University of New South Wales (2019). *Classifying Your Research Data*.
<https://research.unsw.edu.au/classifying-your-research-data>

University of Southampton, School of Electronic and Computer Science (n.d.). *Registry of Open Access Repository Mandates and Policies (ROARMAP)*. <http://roarmap.eprints.org/>

VandeVusse, Alicia & Mueller, Jennifer (2021). 'Data for: Qualitative Data Sharing: Participant Understanding, Motivation, and Consent'. *Qualitative Data Repository*. <https://doi.org/10.5064/F6YYA3O3> QDR Main Collection. V1

Emily M Weitzenboeck, Pierre Lison, Malgorzata Cydecka & Malcolm Langford (2022).
‘The GDPR and Unstructured Data: is Anonymization Possible?’, *International Data Privacy Law*, 2022, ipac008, <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipac008>